

ASSET GROWTH AND PROFITABILITY OF LISTED MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM POST ADOPTION PERIOD OF IFRSs

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Abstract

There is a long-standing argument that asset types and asset growth contribute to the profitability of a company. However, the conclusions of some studies have shown otherwise. Hence, the need for the study. The aim of this study was to examine the influence of asset growth on profitability of the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The research design adopted in the study was ex-post facto owing to the fact that the study required secondary data. The population of the study was thirty-three (33) manufacturing companies whose shares were quoted on the floor of Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG) as at 31st December 2019. Twenty-four (24) entities were selected as sample size of the study based on availability of published annual reports. Historical data for the study were collected from the sampled companies for the period of 2013 to 2019. The nature of data was panel data. The dependent variable was Profitability (PRT) while the independent variable was Asset Growth (AG) sub-divided into Non-Current Asset Growth (NCAG), Current Asset Growth (CAG), Net Asset Growth (NAG) and Total Asset Growth (TAG). The descriptive statistics and simple linear regression statistical tools were used to analyse the relevant data collected for the study. All analysis was conducted at 5% level of significance. From the outcomes of the analysis, it was discovered that NCAG, NAG and TAG had positive and significant influence on PRT ($P < 0.05$) of the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and CAG had positive and insignificant influence on PRT ($P > 0.05$) of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. From the findings, it was concluded that asset growth had a positive and significant influence on profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It was recommended that non-current assets should be acquired and accumulated by the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria as non-current asset growth had positive and significant influence on profitability of these companies and more investments in current asset should be made to contribute more to profitability as this result revealed liquidity challenges.

Keywords: Asset Growth, Profitability, and Quoted Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria.

1. INTRODUCTION

The predominant expectation of the various stakeholders of companies is that the entities should grow continuously because growth guarantees survival and going concern. One of the ways of assessing the growth of entities is to determine the extent to which profitability have been improved. Asset has always been one of the key drivers of profitability of entities both locally and internationally. This is why companies that operate with inadequate assets cannot meet up with their targeted financial performance. To raise profitability is often the main reason why more investments are made on the acquisition and accumulation of assets. For the fact that assets have strong connection with financial performance (profitability) of companies, there is always a need to raise the value of assets over the years for the purpose of improving the profitability. The process of raising the value of assets either by acquisition or accumulation often result in asset growth (Fajaria & Isnalita, 2018). To maximize the wealth of shareholders and to meet up with the expectations of other stakeholders as well, profitability should be enhanced over the years. Profitability represents the total returns from investment of a company and for profits to be maximized, firms' attributes within the control of the management must be effectively and efficiently scrutinized because it is often expected that these factors should drive profitability.

Firm-specific attributes or characteristics are those factors in an entity that are within the control of management of the company. This simply means that for a variable to be an attribute of a company, the management must have the power to influence such variable or factor. These attributes include liquidity, size, revenue growth, asset growth, capital structure or leverage, working capital management, asset management and among others (Babalola, 2013; Fazli, Sam, & Hoshino, 2013). These factors could be effectively managed for the purpose of improvement in profitability. Asset growth is the focus of this study. In every business operation, asset is a resource that is used to derive profitability (Inyiama, Ugbor & Nnenna, 2017). This is owing to the fact that when an entity acquires more assets, it is expected that the company is investing its capital in order to reap more profits. This is why an asset is defined as a resource controlled by an entity from which future economic benefits are expected to flow into the company. Assets are broadly classified into two categories regarded-as non-current assets and current assets. Non-current assets, as the name implies, are those assets that are used for revenue generation by a company for more than one accounting period. They are made up of Properties, Plant and Equipment (PPE), Investment Properties, Intangibles and so on. These compositions of non-current assets can further be sub-divided into plant and machinery, furniture and fittings, motor vehicle, land and building, others. On the other hand, current assets are assets that are used to generate income in one accounting year. They form part of liquidity position of a company because they are used for day-to-day transactions. They include inventories, account receivables, cash, marketable securities and so on.

In the contemporary time, assets have been considered to be essential element of financial statements in which firms' growth is dependent upon. This is why managers are encouraged to acquire and accumulate more assets over the years. Asset growth is a trend increase between a previous' year and present' year total assets (Ariyani, Pangestuti & Raharjo, 2018). When there is an increase in assets acquired between the last year amount and the present year' amount, thus, it can be said that there is an asset growth in the period. This often cut across the two basic classifications of assets which are non-current assets and current assets. Often time, it is expected that non-current assets should grow more than the current assets. Owing to the fact that non-current assets usually have direct influence on profitability of entities as much current assets held can even hinder profitability growth of a firm since idle cash does not generate any return (Suhadak & Handayani, 2018). Asset growth could be in form of non-current asset, current asset, net asset or total asset. When there is asset growth at a particular period of time, it can be said that at that period, the company must have acquired non-current asset (investment in non-current asset) or raise its current asset level (Ugwu & Eze, 2018). In this case, the profit can either be affected positively or negatively depending on the kind of asset that is really growing.

Profitability is simply the difference between all the costs or expenses and the total revenue at a particular period of time. Both (revenue and expenses) are elements of financial statements and are captured in the statement of profits or loss account and other comprehensive income. When there is an increase in profit of a company, it is often said that there is profitability growth for that period. Profit growth is very essential to investors as it helps to raise the value of shares in the market (Odusanya, Yinusa & Ilo, 2018). For instance, a larger profit after tax (profit for the year) for a period can raise the value of Earning Per Share (EPS) of the period. There are many measures of profitability, and these are gross profit margin, net profit margin, return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and among others.

Before now, some of the studies already carried out by other researchers claimed that asset growth had insignificant influence on the financial performance of companies both locally and internationally. Other studies claimed that only non-current asset growth could raise profitability of firms (Okwo, Ugwunta & Nweze, 2012; John & Adebayo, 2013; Mirza & Javed, 2013; Inyiyama *et al.*, 2017). In Nigeria particularly, the period after the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) were not considered by previous researchers. For these reasons and in the literature, it could be said that there are conflicting results in respect of asset growth and profitability of companies. Moreover, in all these studies conducted by other researchers, the companies considered were not as large as those in this study under the class of quoted manufacturing entities in Nigeria. In this regard, it is expected that this on asset growth and profitability of listed manufacturing entities in Nigeria would produce different views on the subject. The burning question is as firms invest in acquisition of assets over the years, has any effect on the profitability of the companies optimistically and materially?

This is the essence of this study. The present study only considered the period after the adoption of IFRSs by public listed companies in Nigeria which is from 2013 to 2019. The main objective of the study was to determine the influence of asset growth on profitability of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 The Meaning of Profitability

One of the yardsticks that guarantee the existence of the listed companies in Nigeria is profitability (Irungu, 2017). This is why all the strategies formulated by board of directors of entities are tailored towards profitability. In order to elaborate on profitability, it is pertinent to properly explain profit in the light of accounting. Profit is defined as the difference between selling price and cost price of a product or service (Suhadak & Handayani, 2018). This is a simple way of understanding the meaning of profit. It is also the difference between revenue and various costs incurred. According to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs), costs and expenses are collapsed together to be often used interchangeably but the structure of accounting places different kinds of costs in order of occurrence in financial statements (Melville, 2014). In preparing the statement of profit or loss account, the charges that constitute costs or expenses are cost of sales, administration expenses/costs, distribution costs, finance costs and income tax expenses.

Cost of sales include various expenses that are directly associated with the products or services of companies (Cyril & Ogbonna, 2013). For a manufacturing company, composition of cost of sales includes total costs of production, which are prime costs plus factory overhead and inventories in finished goods. In order word, the summation cost of raw materials consumed, manufacturing wages (direct costs), factory overhead (indirect costs) and inventories in finished goods. For a service or merchandise company where products are not manufactured, the composition of cost of sales is inventories of goods, purchases and carriage inwards. When cost of sales is deducted from the total revenue of a company we arrive at gross profits or losses depending on the value of revenue (Abubakar, Sulaiman & Haruna, 2018).

Administration costs/expenses are costs incurred mainly to maintain the workforce of an entity at a particular period of time. They are mainly incurred on human technical skills and manpower (human resources). As the name indicates, administration expenses are costs incurred on operational activities of companies that require the skills and strength of human. They include salaries and wages of employees, salaries and wages of directors, audit fees, medical expenses of employees and directors, travelling expenses of employees and directors, pension costs of employees and directors, gratuity of employees and directors, welfare of employees and directors and other general expenses. In accordance with IFRSs, all the listed companies have the same contents of administration expenses/costs, but although different names can be given to individual expenses that constitute administration (Melville, 2014). Distribution costs/expenses are costs incurred in

selling and distribution of goods and services of companies. They include marketing of companies' product and services to the general public, bonuses and commission paid for targets met and other costs that are associated with selling and distribution of goods and services. The essence of distribution costs is to ensure that companies' products and services get to the various target consumers as production is not complete until the goods produced gets to the final consumers (Megaladevi, 2018). When both administration and distribution costs/expenses are deducted from gross profits or losses we arrive at operating profits or losses also known as Earnings Before Interest and Taxes (EBIT).

Finance costs are costs incurred on borrowed funds used to carry out operational activities of companies. They are regarded as cost of debt capital (Pandey, 2010; Konak & Güner, 2016). Finance costs include interest on bank overdraft, interest on bank loan or loan notes. When finance costs are deducted from operating profits or losses, we have profits or losses before taxes. Income taxes are the aggregate of all forms of taxes paid to government usually a year. Income taxes are not expenses incurred on companies' activities directly but a compulsory levy that must be paid to government to support infrastructural development by government (John & Adebayo, 2013). When income taxes are deducted from profits or losses before taxes, we have profits for the year (profits after taxes). Based on these explanations, we have different categories of profits, and they are gross profits, operating profits, profits before taxes and profits after taxes. The focus of this study is on profits after taxes.

Profitability is simply the measurement of success achieved by companies in selling their products beyond the costs incurred (Pandey, 2010). It can also be said to be the mark-up charged when selling the goods and services of companies. Profitability is the main essence of establishing entities because of the fact that profit maximization is the expected returns of any company. Maximization of profitability is the reason why strategies are formulated by management of companies (Megaladevi, 2018). For the fact that profitability is the measurement of success accomplished by companies but however, it does not indicate the real financial status of entities because of the following reasons which include firstly, non-cash items are often deducted from the statement of profit or loss account in computation of accounting profits. The non-cash items often included in the computation of profits are depreciation, provision for bad debts, losses from disposal of assets and among others (Bolek & Grosicki, 2012). This renders accounting profit unrealistic. In order to reduce unrealistic effects of accounting profits, non-cash items should be estimated in conservative manner, by either reducing the numbers of non-cash items or cutting down the costs on non-cash items to be incorporated in the statement of profit or loss account.

Secondly, larger profits declared by companies do not mean that at hand, they have the money. For instance, when the greater proportion of revenue are on credit, it therefore means that the larger proportion of the profits declared are nothing but paper profits because there is no assurance that the total account receivables are

always recovered completely and on time. Some of the account receivables that are meant for an accounting period can be recovered by companies in five years' time and some can even turn out to be irrecoverable debts (bad debts). In order to reduce this effects, greater proportion of revenue for a year should be in cash. Thirdly and finally, accounting profits are not computed in line with the changes in the rate of inflation. The accounting profits are always nominal not real because they are computed without taking into consideration the changes in the rate of inflation. This is why the returns from assets accumulated cannot purchase reasonable quantity of goods and services in the market and a sudden increase in the rate of inflation can throw companies' financial performance off-balance (Grace, Ann & Onodugo, 2016). In IFRSs, the accounting standards do not support the preparation of financial statements with the inclusion of changes in inflation rate.

Profitability ratios of entities can be measured using different indicators such as Gross Profit Margin (GPM), Operating Profit Margin (OPM), Net Profit Margin (NPM), Returns on Assets (ROA), Returns on Equity (ROE) and Returns on Capital Employed (ROCE) and among others (Pandey, 2010). These are explained below:

i. Gross Profit Margin (GPM): Gross profit is defined as the difference between revenue and cost of sales of an entity for a particular period of time. Gross profit is the profit achieved when the total cost of sales is deducted from total revenue. Gross profit affects all the stakeholders of a business simply because of the fact that the stake of employees, investors, government, managers, shareholders have not been deducted (Akinleye & Adeboboye, 2019). GPM is calculated as total gross profit divided by total revenue for period of time. The GPM is a profitability ratio that links all the stakeholders of a company together. This is owing to the fact that in the computation of gross profit, interest of other stakeholders, such as administration and distribution costs, finance costs, income taxes and so on, are not deducted.

ii. Operating Profit Margin (OPM): Operating profit is the difference between gross profit, administration expenses and distribution costs of an entity at a period (Sanjaya & Jayasiri, 2017). It could also be defined as the difference between revenue, cost of sales, administration expenses and distribution costs of a company. It is the profits arrived after deducting the interest of the employees, directors and other human costs/expenses. OPM is calculated as operating profit divided by total revenue at a time. OPM is a financial performance indicator that connects the government, creditors and the shareholders. This is because in the calculation of operating profit, the interest of the stakeholders, such as the government, creditors and the shareholders, are inclusive.

iii. Profit Before Tax Margin (PBTM): Profit before tax is defined as the difference between operating profit or earnings before interest and tax (EBIT) and finance costs (Abdulazeez, Baba, Fatima & Abdulrahaman, 2018). Profit before tax is arrived at after the stake of debt holders are deducted from the operating profit of a company. the interests that constitute the finance costs are for both short-termed and long-termed debts capital. On the other hand, PBTM is computed as total profits before taxes divided by total revenue for an accounting period.

iv. Net Profit Margin (NPM): Net profit is defined as the difference between revenue, cost of sales, administration expenses, distribution costs, finance costs and income taxes of an entity for a particular period of time. Profits for the year (profits after taxes) are attained after deducting the total income taxes for the accounting period (Abubakar *et al.*, 2018). It is the profits that belong to equity shareholders. Proportion of this profits can be paid as dividends to preference shareholders or equity shareholders while some portion retained. Thus, profits for the year are often seen as the amount available to the shareholders (both preference and equity shareholders) that can either be distributed or retained for future growth of the company. In some conditions, companies' directors may choose to retain the whole of their profits for a year either to finance long-termed projects or to strengthen the operating activities of their companies. NPM is calculated as net profit divided by total revenue at a time. The NPM is financial performance indicator that relates to the shareholders of a company.

Profits for the year of a company can be used to compute the ROE, ROA and as well as the EPS.

v. Return on Assets (ROA): ROA is calculated as total profits for the year divided by the total assets for an accounting period. This ratio measures the capability of the firm to generate profit by using its total assets. Thus, this ratio indicates how efficiently the assets of the company are employed to generate profit. The higher the ROA ratio, the better the company is using its own recourses and vice versa. This is owing to the fact that as more assets are acquired, it is expected that profitability should grow along with the trend of assets accumulated. When ROA is adopted as the proxy of profitability, it is believed that the total assets of the entity are key to revenue and profit generation of the company (Manyo & Ogakwu, 2013). The researchers used ROA as profitability indicator or proxy because it is more concerned with the association between total profits and assets accumulated. The listed companies in Nigeria are driving towards expansion and one of the yardsticks for measuring the level of expansion of an entity is the total assets which constitute the independent variables. Assets are used to generate revenue, which can raise profitability. This simply means that without the acquisition of assets or investment in assets, profitability of any company cannot grow actively. This is why ROA is considered appropriate because the researchers wished to evaluate how far the various independent variables have contributed to the profitability of listed companies in Nigeria.

vi. Return on Equity (ROE): ROE is a ratio that shows how much profit a firm earned compared to the total amount of shareholders' total equity reported on the statement of financial position for a period (Kothari & Sodha, 2019). ROE measures how far the stockholders' funds are used to generate revenue over a period of time. A company that has a high return on equity is expected to be one that is able to generate revenue by effective utilization of equity shareholders' funds.

vii. Return on Capital Employed (ROCE): The ROCE is computed as operating profits divided by total assets less current liabilities of a company for a period of time. The profits considered in computing the ROCE is after deducting distribution and administration expenses of a company for the accounting period (Mirza & Javed, 2013; Daat, Sanggenafa, & Larasati, 2021). The ROCE indicates how far an entity has been able to use shareholders' funds and long-termed debt capital (non-current liabilities) to generate revenue for a particular period of time.

2.1.2 Meaning of Assets and Asset Growth

Before the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) by countries, asset has been defined in accordance with individual country's Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP). Their definitions of asset were based on perception of what they think to constitute an asset of entities (Fajaria and Isnalita, 2018). During these time, comparability of performance by companies was impaired because of the fact that financial statements prepared then by entities in the world were not uniform and what was classified as assets in one jurisdiction were not regarded as assets in another jurisdiction. This was the greatest problem with individual country's GAAP. Some of these countries' definitions of asset as at then are as follows: firstly, an asset was defined as the property of a business that is used to generate income; Secondly, an asset was defined as the tangibles items of a business that can be seen, felt and touched (Inyama *et al.*, 2017); Thirdly, assets were regarded as the stock of capital or total investments of an entity and finally, asset were seen as all tangible and intangible items of a business used for one and more than one accounting periods. It is the last definition of asset above that gave a picture of what was practiced as assets before the adoption of IFRSs in the world. This is because of the fact that the definition contains the different classifications of assets such as fixed, tangible and intangible and as well as current assets. Other definitions stated above, we have seen clearly that assets were described as the tangible properties only and that can be seen physically; they were regarded as total investment by some countries, and they were known to be any item used to generate income.

Since the adoption of IFRSs by countries in the world was made possible, definitions of all accounting terms are harmonized in order to encourage uniformity of financial statements prepared by different companies in the world today and to enhance comparison annual and different entities' performance. The adoption of IFRSs help to solve the problem of inconsistency and uniformity of financial statements of companies (Melville, 2014). Asset is one of these accounting terms that is consistently defined by IFRSs' conceptual framework. According to IFRSs' conceptual framework, an asset is defined as a resource controlled by an entity as a result of past transactions from which future economic benefits are expected to flow into the entity. This definition of asset is widely acceptable and also contained fundamental elements that even assist in both the recognition and measurement of asset in financial statements.

The major elements in the definition of asset are resources, the possibility of being controlled, past transactions, the possibility of having future economic benefits. All these factors stated must be together before an item of expenditure can be regarded as an asset. For anything to be regarded as an asset, it must be a resource as well. A resource is defined as both tangible and intangible thing that is used to carryout business activities. Resource includes skills of man, materials, machine, money and information (Pandey, 2010). A simple way of describing resources is by using the acronym known as “Four Ms plus I” which stands for man, material, machine, money and information. Men are resources of entities which are regarded as employees, directors and among others. They often use skills and strength to carryout operational activities of companies.

Materials are resources that require further processing to attain companies' products. This is more common in manufacturing entities where raw materials are used to produce finished goods of companies. In this case, materials are assets that are used for further production of other goods. Materials are classified as current assets of companies because they are often used for daily production of entities' required products. Machine is defined as equipment or plans used to carryout manufacturing activities of a companies (Chandrapala & Knápková, 2013). It is often used to quicken the production of goods and services in larger quantity which can take a lot of time if those commodities are to be manufactured manually. Thus, the major advantages of using machine in production process are for the purpose of mass production, to save time, to maintain quality and to reduce costs. Machine is part of composition of non-current assets known as property, plant and equipment (PPE) (Ugwu & Eze, 2018). Money is made up of short financial instruments that are traded in financial market non as money market. Money are resources needed for day-to-day transaction. They constitute component of current asset of companies. money as are assets is made up of cash in hand, cash in bank and all the cash equivalent such as short-term marketable security like treasuring build, certificate of deposits and among others.

Information is defined as resources, although intangible, needed to carryout operational activities of companies. From the definition, information belongs to the category of intangible assets under non-current assets (Suhadak & Handayani, 2018). Information is essential in the modern business activities because of the challenging nature in the aspect of competition and as well as their dynamic nature. This is why information is seen as an exceptional type of resources. Basically, there are two categories of information which are bad and good information. Bad information is information that cannot add value to operational activities of any company in accounting perspective (Mirza & Javed, 2013). This simply means that any information that do not relate to operational activities of companies are bad information. To differentiate between bad and good information, there are certain attributes that must be embedded in so-called information.

These attributes or qualities are understandability, purpose and relevance, reliability, sufficiently complete, timeliness, comparability, communicated to the right person and its value must exist costs. These are qualities that make information available good or essential for decision making. Thus, good information is information, when use as yardstick for decision making, can add value to operational activities of companies which can either be employees' productivities, turnover, increase in market share or improvement in financial performance. For information to have the attribute of been understood, it must be stated clearly and be properly explain for the users to assimilate. For information to have the quality of purpose or relevance, is simply that information must be essentials to the intended use.

For information to be reliable, it simply means that the available information must be accurate for decision to be based upon. For information to have the quality of being insufficiently complete, it simply means that information should include only key items that are necessary for decision making. For information to have the quality of being timely, is simply means that available information should be provided at the right time for decision making purpose. For information to have the quality of being compared, they should be able to make comparison possible by being prepared using the same basis or methods (Pervan & Višić, 2012). Information should be communicated to the right person would use them to make useful decision. Finally, the value of information must be greater than the costs incurred to obtain the information. On the contrary, if the costs of obtaining information is greater than the value or benefit to gets, such information should be regarded as bad information. The main purpose of getting information is summarised into planning, controlling and decision-making purposes.

For anything to be constituted as assets of entities, the companies must have the ability to control the asset (Soewarno & Tjahjadi, 2020). In this case, entities need not to own the assets before they can control. However, anything regarded as assets need not to be purchased fully by a company but in as much as it is within the custody of a company for business purpose, it is known as assets. For an item of assets should be control by an entity, the company must be able to use the assets to generate revenue or income for the purpose of the company's growth (Ugwu & Eze, 2018). These simply means that when a company staff uses company van to generate income for his household, in this case, the company does not have full control of the assets owing to the fact that the income generated with the use of the company's vehicle do not form part of the returns for the company. Assets of entity do not just exist on their own rather, it is as a result of transaction that took place in the past. This is while the costs of acquisition of assets are always historical in nature. It indicates that for total assets of any company to exist, they must have been acquired in the past. Historical costs of assets are one of the bases of measurement of elements of financial statements often recognised on the statements.

For an accounting item to be regarded as assets, there must be future economic benefit flowing into the company that control the assets (Cyril & Ogonna, 2013).

Economic benefits as to do with income which can be generated with the use of assets. They include revenue, returns from investment and among others. Economic benefits may be directly or indirectly flowing into entity's operation. Direct economic are the type of economic benefits that companies usually achieved with the direct usage of the assets. For instance, interest that company usually get from treasuring bill, income from trademark (intangible assets) and returns from other investments are regarded as direct economic benefits. On the other hand, indirectly economic benefits are the benefits derived by companies through costs saving which occur as a result of usage of the companies' assets (John & Adebayo, 2013). For instance, motor vehicle often used for delivery of goods and services owned by a company helps to save the company's costs/expenses that should have been paid to hire a motor van to deliver the company's products to the customers' destinations. This is how economic benefits could flow indirectly to company' operations because the costs saved can form part of revenue or income to the company.

In accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs), assets are basically classified into two (Melville, 2014) known as:

i. Non-Current Assets: These are asset acquired by an entity to be use in generate income for longer period of time which is more than one accounting period. This simply means that non-current assets are those assets that are acquired with the common motive of using them to generate income for a longer period of time (Okwo *et al.*, 2012). Non-current assets include property, plant and equipment (PPE), investment properties, intangible assets and among others. Property, plant and equipment is defined as tangible items that are held for use in the production or supply of goods or services, for renter to others, or for an administrative purpose and are expected to be use for more than one accounting period. This definition covers all the tangible items that can be regarded as PPE of the company. PPE include the following such as machineries, furniture and fittings, land and building held for production and so on. Investment properties are regarded as land or building, or part of building held to earn renter income or for capital appreciation or both. In this case, a company that owns a building for a renter purpose is set to have investment property other than PPE. Intangible assets are defined as an identifiable, non-monetary asset without physical substance (Ariyani *et al.*, 2018). This simply means that a non-current asset can exist without a physical form.

ii. Current Assets: These are assets expected to be use in one accounting period usually one year. in other word, current assets are those assets that can easily converted into cash without the loss of substantial face value during the conversion (Akinleye & Adeboboye, 2019). Current assets include inventory, account receivable, cash and marketable securities such as treasury bills. Inventories are stock of goods that are expected to be sold in one accounting period. In this case, stock of raw material, working in progress and finished goods all constitute inventories. Inventory of raw materials are stock of goods held by companies for further production of finished goods. Inventory of work in progress are stock of partly manufacture goods expected to be fully completed in another accounting

period. Inventory of finished goods are stock of completed goods that are expected to be sold in one accounting period (Pandey, 2010). Account receivables are short-term debt from which inflows of cash are expected to flow into an entity in one accounting period. This simply means that account receivable are short-term assets expected to be converted into cash to meet up with current obligations of companies that fall due. Cash are defined as total amount of money at hand, total amount of money in bank and all the marketable securities.

Asset, as an element of financial statements, is fundamental to every entity because of its role played in generate income. This is while managers of company always ensure that assets are properly maintained in order for the overall performance to improve. Assets are being seen as a profit driver that can raise the entire performance of an entities. Asset growth is a basis to achieved improvement in profitability (Inyiama *et al.*, 2017). In this regard, asset growth is defined as a positive increment in the value or carrying amount of total assets of an entity. It could also be defined as a positive trend difference between the present's year value of assets and the previous' year value of assets. The essence of acquisition of more assets in operational activities of any company is to raise the profitability of that entity. So, when assets of companies continue to grow, it can be said strategically that profitability of those entities are improving continuously as well. Asset growth can be any of the following stated below:

i. Non-Current Asset Growth: This occurs when only the components of non-current asset are acquired often by management of companies. When this occurs, the total non-current assets continue to grow. For instance, when an entity acquires/build new branches in different locations, in this case, non-current asset can grow and at the same time the total sale revenue derived in those branches can help to improve the profitability of the entire company. This classification of assets helped to generate revenue more than the other classification of assets and eventually profitability. Non-current assets growth can be caused by the acquisition of any of the following such as PPE, intangible assets or investment properties (Okwo *et al.*, 2012). When a company acquired more PPE for modernization or expansion, non-current assets of the company can grow. Also, when a company discovered new intangible assets and capitalized it on the statements of financial position, non-current assets can also grow. In this regard, when management of companies want to ascertain the growth in their non-current assets, they would always check the amount of money committed to acquire any of the components of the non-current assets in a particular year.

ii. Current Asset Growth: This occurs when only the components of current asset are acquired often by management of companies (Babalola, 2013). When this occurs, the total current assets continue to grow. It is often said that the higher the current asset, the lower the profitability of a company as idle funds do not generate any returns and vice versa. So, accumulate more current assets in a company's operation should be discouraged and current assets should not be too small so that it will not result to overtrading where current obligations that fall due are not settled

(Pervan, Pervan & Ćurak, 2017; Abdulazeez *et al.*, 2018). Considering the fact that operational activities of entities expand over the years, the current asset for a present year should be greater than that of the previous year in order to enable companies to meet up with changes in the markets. The various components of current assets are inventories, account receivable and cash. For there to be growth in current assets, any of the components or all the components must grow as well. Accumulating more current assets might affect the overall performance of companies adversely. For this reason, managers of entities should be able to strike a balance between current assets and profitability where the total current assets accumulated can affect the profitability of the companies optimistically.

iii. Net Asset Growth: Net asset is defined as the total assets of an entity less the current liabilities for the accounting period (Odusanya *et al.*, 2018; Anik, Chariri & Isgiyarta, 2021). It could also be said to be the sum of shareholders' equity and long-termed debt capital (non-current liabilities) of companies for an accounting period which is usually a year. Net asset growth is simply a trend increase in long-termed capital, which consists of shareholders' funds and non-current liabilities, of a company for a particular year compared to previous year. As net asset of an entity improves, it could be explained that during this period, the firm has an increment in capital attributable to both equity and long-termed debt used to finance its operational activities to derive optimal benefits for the company (Alpon *et al.*, 2019 and Hesniati, 2021). So, as net asset grows continuously, it is expected that the profitability of companies should be raised on the same trend. This is always the focus of every management of entities.

iv. Total Asset Growth: Total asset is often the aggregate of both non-current assets and current assets of companies. For this reason, total asset growth is defined as a positive increment in the value or carrying amount of total assets of an entity. It could also be defined as a positive trend difference between the present's year value of total assets and the previous' year value of assets (Ariyani *et al.*, 2018; Soewarno & Tjahjadi, 2020). When total assets grow, it could be said that more funds derived from both equity and debts were used to finance the operational activities to achieve more profits. In this case, debt capital is made up of both short-termed and long-termed sources. For total assets to grow, some or all the components of assets which include PPE, intangible assets, investment properties, inventories, account receivables and cash must increase in an accounting period. For this to affect the profitability of companies optimistically, the current asset classification of assets must be properly managed. This is regarded as liquidity management by researchers.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Stakeholder Theory

This theory was developed and advanced by Richard Edward Freeman (1984). The purpose of the formulation of this theory was because of the fact that the various activities of companies are believed to affect those with both direct and indirect interests. For one to be a stakeholder in an entity, he/she must contribute directly or

indirectly to the existence of such company. There are different categories of stakeholders but for simplicity, the major kinds of stakeholders are government, employees, creditors, shareholders, competitors, customers, local communities, suppliers and among others. The interest of government is tied to income taxes payable by a company and which constitutes the revenue of the government; the interest of employees is tied to job security and the continuous inflows of income in form of salaries and wages they often receive routinely; the interest of creditors is mostly on interest from the total amount borrowed to an entity and as well as the principal amount at maturity of the period agreed; the interest of competitors is mostly on the existence of other companies for the kind of strategies adopted to be successful in the markets; the interest of customers is mostly on the existence of companies for the kind of products offered to the markets; the interest of local communities is tied to corporate social responsibilities presented by companies to local dwellers where those entities are located and the interest of the suppliers is on the liquidity position of companies in order for them to be paid for goods supplied on account to the firms.

From the above elaboration, it is pertinent to say all the stakeholders have different interests in the existence of companies. The theory upholds that companies should be managed in such a way that the various interests of the stakeholders are affected optimistically. According to Freeman (1984) the theory does not highlight that the interests of all the stakeholders should be satisfied at the same time, however, it states that the various interests of the stakeholders are satisfied on step-by-step approach, and this is why general-purpose financial statements are always required to be presented to users irrespective of their diverse interests. The theory states that an entity should be managed in a way that would affect the primary stakeholders first who are the providers of funds and the real owners of the company before other stakeholders.

The primary stakeholders are referred to as the shareholders and other creditors who usually provide both debt and equity capital to carry out operational activities which include acquisition of non-current assets, current asset management and so on. The theory also upholds that the interests of the primary stakeholders should be attained and satisfied first because of the fact that they are the lifeblood of the existence of any entity. For the interests of the aggregate stakeholders to be satisfied, the profits of companies must be optimized. Maximization of profits guarantee growth in the wealth of the shareholders and as well as other stakeholders. In order to accomplish optimality in profitability of companies, assets must be acquired and managed in lined with revenue growth and profit maximization. In a study of asset growth and profitability of listed companies, managers will be expose to how far they have been able to manage their classified assets to foster profitability growth.

Strategies of directors of any company are directed to ensure that the key variables that are capable of driving the growth in profitability of the firms are identified.

Inclusion of these strategies is the acquisition of non-current assets. In this regard, management focuses more attention on those variables in order to bring the best out for the entity. The variables that drive the growth in profitability of an entity cannot remain the same over time. This is owing to the fact that things change as time elapses. For instance, when there are changes in technology, new ideas are invented and so on. Therefore, it is advice able that management of any entity should always evaluate the variables considered as the key performance indicators as time passes to find out whether or not those variables are still the key performance to the firm. If those variables are not still the key performance indicators to companies because of passage of time, performance appraisal must be carried out to identify new performance indicators to the entities.

The theory is related to the present study because of the fact the primary expectation of all the stakeholders of listed companies in Nigeria is that the profitability should grow continuously so that these companies exist perpetually in the industry and their going concern will be assured as well. From these views, we can see that managers have role to play in raising the profitability of companies most especially, using assets. This is because of the fact that poor performance of any company must always affect some group of stakeholders negatively. So, it is the duty of the management of company to ensure that sound policies are made in order to cause the classified assets to affect the profitability optimistically and materially. Hence, the researchers adopted the theory in this study.

2.3 Empirical Review

Cyril & Ogbonna (2013) assessed the influence of investment in non-current assets on return on asset (ROA) of listed cement manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The independent variables considered were all the elements of non-current assets of the firms, while the dependent variable was ROA. Relevant data were obtained from 2004 to 2013. From the analysis, it was observed that plant and machinery exerted adequate impact on profitability of the companies studied.

Inyama *et al.* (2017) in a study to evaluate the level of association between assets growth rate and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The focus was to empirically evaluate the level of association between asset growth and profitability of companies studied. The *ex-post facto* research design was employed in the study because of the fact the technique for data collection was secondary. Six (6) companies were drawn as sample size for the study from the population size of twenty-two (22) manufacturing companies listed on the floor of the NSE. Relevant data were collected from the published financial statements of the sampled companies for ten years' period from 2006 to 2015. The independent variables were proxied with Non-current asset growth rate, current asset growth rate and net asset growth rate and the dependent variable (financial performance) was proxied with profit after tax. The sourced data were analysed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression technique. From the analysis, it was discovered that non-current asset growth rate and net asset growth rate of the companies optimistically

and powerfully related with the profit after tax. It was also found that current asset growth rate optimistically and immaterially associated with the profit after tax of the companies studied. It was recommended that manufacturing companies in Nigeria should increase their non-current assets and net assets value by increasing their total assets and reducing the components of their current liabilities and also, they should increase their current assets, but should keep it at an optimum level that will ensure that maturing short-term obligations are met to avoid keeping excess idle funds.

Irungu (2017) evaluated the effect of liquidity on financial performance of listed firms in the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). The *ex-post facto* research design was employed in the study owing to the fact that the sources for data collection were secondary. Census sampling technique was used to study the entire population size of sixty-four (64) companies listed. However, the obtained data for the study were analysed with the use of linear regression technique. Findings indicated that liquidity had a positive and significant effect on financial performance of financial and non-financial companies. It was concluded that liquidity had a positive and significant influence on the financial performance of listed firms in the NSE.

Ariyani *et al.* (2018) carried out a study to investigate the effect of asset structure, profitability, company size, and company growth on capital structure manufacturing companies in Indonesia. The focus of the researchers was to determine the influence of asset structure, profitability, firm size and company growth on the capital structure of companies studied. Relevant data in relation to the variables of the study were obtained from the published financial statements of companies chosen for study and for the period of 2013 to 2017. The purposive sampling technique was used, and fifty-two (52) companies were sampled for the study. The sourced data were analysed with the use of multiple linear regression technique and other inferential statistics. From the analysis, it was discovered that asset structure had an optimistic and immaterial effect on the capital structure, profitability had an adverse and irrelevant effect on the capital structure, size of the company had an encouraging and substantial effect on the capital structure, and the company's growth had an undesirable and substantial effect on the capital structure.

Suhadak & Handayani (2018) carried out a study to determine the influence of profitability, solvability, asset growth, and sales growth on firm value mining companies in Indonesia. The intention of the researchers was to empirically investigate the extent to which internal factors had affected firm value of companies studied. The independent variables (internal factors) considered in the study were profitability, solvability, asset growth, and sales growth and firm value was the dependent variable. The relevant data were obtained from the published financial statements of the companies sampled for study. The obtained data were analysed with the use of multiple linear regression technique. From the analysis, it was observed that profitability, solvability, asset growth, and sales growth had jointly material influence on the firm value. Individually, profitability and sales growth had no substantial influence on firm value while solvability and asset growth had material effect on the firm value.

Ugwu & Eze (2018) conducted a study to empirically determine the effect of firms' growth indices on profitability of food and beverage firms in Nigeria. The intention of the researchers was to investigate how far firms' growth indices had affected the profitability of the companies chosen for study. The correlational research design was employed in the study because of the fact that the technique for collection of data was secondary. Relevant data were collected from the published financial statements of companies chosen for study in the floor of the NGX for the period of 2001 to 2016. The collected data were analysed using multiple linear regression technique. From the analysis, it was observed that total assets had substantial effect on firm performance in Nigeria; market value had substantial effect on firm performance in Nigeria; and firm size had material effect on firm performance in Nigeria. However, it was recommended that companies should endeavour to maintain increased assets to boost their performance.

Alpon *et al.* (2019) in a study to analyse the effect of asset growth, profitability and company size on capital structure of mining companies in Indonesia (empirical study in mining sector companies in Indonesia Stock Exchange). The intention of the researchers was to determine empirically the effect of asset growth rate, profitability and firm size on capital structure of the companies studied. The quantitative research was employed in the study owing to the fact that the technique for relevant data collection was secondary. The purposive sampling technique was used to draw a sample size of seventy-six (76) mining companies listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2011 to 2014. The multiple linear regression technique was used to analyse the sourced data. From the analysis, it was discovered that asset growth rate had adverse and irrelevant effect on capital structure of the listed companies studied; profitability had undesirable and substantial effect on capital structure of the listed companies studied and firm size had optimistic and substantial effect on capital structure of the listed companies studied.

2.3.1 Gap in the Literature

In all the studies reviewed both locally and internationally and to the best of the researcher's knowledge, none of the studies examined the influence of asset growth on profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study of Inyama *et al.* (2017) was conducted only in manufacturing companies quoted on NGX and six (6) companies were drawn as sample size for the study; the study of Ugwu & Eze (2018) was carried on listed food and beverage firms; the study of Cyril & Ogbonna (2013) was carried out to determine the influence of non-current assets on profitability of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and the study of Ariyani *et al.* (2018) was conducted in Indonesia.

Thus, the present study would add to the literature by taking into consideration a larger sample size drawn from the consumer goods companies and industrial goods companies traded on the floor of Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and independent variables such as non-current asset growth, current asset growth, net asset growth and as well as total asset growth and how they affected the profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria with panel data between 2013 to 2019.

3. METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted the *ex-post facto* research design technique. This design was selected because the researcher had no power to influence the data to be collected for the study and the technique for data collection is secondary. The adoption of this research design will enable the researcher to determine the influence of asset growth on profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria without any bias. The population of the study covered the entire listed consumer goods companies and industrial goods companies in Nigeria quoted. The listed consumer goods companies and industrial goods companies on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG) as at 31st December, 2019 were twenty (20) and thirteen (13) respectively and made up the quoted manufacturing companies considered by the researcher in the present study. In this case, the population of the study was thirty-three (33) in number.

The sample size of the study is drawn from the total population of thirty-three (33) listed manufacturing companies in the floor of NSE. Twenty-four (24) listed companies were drawn from the population purposively. The sample size of twenty-four (24) listed companies drawn were made up of fourteen (14) companies from listed consumer goods and ten (10) companies from listed industrial goods in Nigeria. This was in line with the requirements of scholars who stated that at least 10% of total population size is suitable as sample size of a study and can represent the entire population (Gujarati, 2013; Kothari & Garg, 2014). The quoted manufacturing companies used in the sample size were those with well-presented financial statements as single entities in International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) formats. The purposive sampling technique was used in the study.

The data for the study were obtained from the audited and published financial statements in annual reports of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria sampled for the study presented in IFRSs format. The data used were panel data obtained from the year 2013 to 2019. The choice of the period was to capture only the financial statements of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria presented in IFRSs requirements. The dependent variable was Profitability (PRT) measured by Returns on Assets (ROA) while the independent variables were Non-Current Asset Growth (NCAG), Current Asset Growth (CAG), Net Asset Growth (NAG) and Total Asset Growth (TAG). The models were stated in accordance with the relevant variables in the study as:

$$PRT_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NCAG_{ij} + \beta_2 CAG_{ij} + \beta_3 NAG_{ij} + \beta_4 TAG_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.1)}$$

where: i=Number of companies; j=Number of years; β_0 =Intercept of PRT; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 =Coefficient of each of the independent variables; e_t =Random error terms. The above model could be re-stated as:

$$PRT_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NCAG_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.2)}$$

$$PRT_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CAG_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.3)}$$

$$PRT_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NAG_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.4)}$$

$$PRT_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TAG_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.5)}$$

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and simple linear regression models.

4. EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

4.1 Data Analysis

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

To examine the attributes of the essential data collected for the study, descriptive statistics were computed for all the variables and presented on Table 4.1:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	N	Range	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.
PRT	168	2.350	-1.800	0.550	0.046	0.174
NCAG	168	26.810	-1.000	25.810	0.275	2.125
CAG	168	12.980	-1.000	11.980	0.216	1.085
NAG	168	19.350	-1.120	18.230	0.342	1.913
TAG	168	14.110	-1.000	13.110	0.212	1.201

Source: Researchers' Computation (2023)

From Table 4.1, Profitability (PRT) had range, minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of 235% (2.35), -180% (-1.80), 55% (0.55), 4.57% (0.0457) and 17.36% (0.1736) respectively. The range showed the difference between the maximum and minimum value of PRT as 235%, the minimum indicated that the least value of PRT for period of study was -180%, the maximum showed that the highest value of PRT was 55%, the mean indicated an average of PRT made by the entities for the period of the study as 4.57% and the standard deviation of 17.36% indicated that the variation between the data set for PRT from the mean value was high for the period of the present study.

Non-Current Asset Growth (NCAG) had range, minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of 2681% (26.81), -100% (-1.00), 2581% (25.81), 27.48% (0.2748) and 212.46% (2.1246) respectively. The range showed the difference between the maximum and minimum value of NCAG as 2681%, the minimum indicated that the least value of NCAG for period of study was -100%, the maximum showed that the highest value of NCAG was 2581%, the mean indicated average of NCAG attained by the entities for the period of the study as 27.48% and the standard deviation of 212.46% indicated that the variation between the data set for NCAG from the mean value was high for the period of the present study.

Current Asset Growth (CAG) had range, minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of 1298% (12.98), -100% (-1.00), 1198% (11.98), 21.55% (0.2155) and 108.54% (1.0854) respectively. The range showed the difference between the maximum and minimum value of CAG as 1298%, the minimum indicated that the least value of CAG for period of study was -100%, the maximum showed that the highest value of CAG was 1198%, the mean indicated an average of CAG attained by the companies for the period of the study as 21.55% and the standard deviation of 108.54% showed that the variation between the data set for CAG from the mean value was high for the period of the present study.

Net Asset Growth (NAG) had range, minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of 1935% (19.35), -112% (-1.12), 1823% (18.23), 34.24% (0.3424) and 191.27% (1.9127) respectively. The range indicated the difference between the maximum and minimum value of NAG as 1935%, the minimum indicated that the least value of NAG for period of study was -112%, the maximum showed that the highest value of NAG was 1823%, the mean value indicated an average of NAG attained by the firms for the period of the study as 34.24% and the standard deviation of 191.27% showed that the variation between the data set for NAG from the mean value was high for the period of the present study.

Total Asset Growth (TAG) had range, minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation of 1411% (14.11), -100% (-1.00), 1311% (13.11), 21.22% (0.2122) and 120.08% (1.2008) respectively. The range indicated the difference between the maximum and minimum value of TAG as 1411%, the minimum indicated that the least value of TAG for period of study was -100%, the maximum showed that the highest value of TAG was 1311%, the mean value indicated an average of TAG accomplished by the entities for the period of the study as 21.22% and the standard deviation of 120.08% showed that the variation between the data set for TAG from the mean value was high for the period of the present study.

4.1.2 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study were tested with the use of t-statistics, probability value (p-value) and F-ratio as criteria for accepting or rejecting any of the hypotheses (null or alternative hypothesis) computed using simple linear regression.

4.1.2.1 Hypothesis One

The simple linear regression statistics were computed and presented on the Table 4.2:

Table 4.2: Simple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-Value	Remark	R	R ²	Adj R ²	F-ratio
Constant	0.032	3.556	0.000	Significant	0.586	0.343	0.332	24.811, p<0.05
NCAG	0.361	8.805	0.001	Significant				

*Dependent Variable=PRT

Source: Researchers' Computation (2023)

From Table 4.2, NCAG exerted positive and significant influence on PRT (p<0.05) of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It indicated that a percentage increase in NCAG resulted to 36.1% increase in PRT. A constant value showed that PRT was 3.2% as NCAG was held constant and significant (p<0.05). The constant value of 3.2% also indicated that the quoted companies had been making some profits without NCAG. The NCAG was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers of the present study. The correlation coefficient (r) indicated that the

relationship between NCAG and PRT was 58.6%. R^2 (coefficient of determination) showed that 34.3% variation in the PRT was attributed to the influence of NCAG in the model. The F-ratio (24.811, prob.<0.05) calculated indicated that the model was significant. The null hypothesis, which stated that non-current asset growth does not significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that non-current asset growth significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted because both t-statistics and the p-value showed that NCAG was significant.

4.1.2.2 Hypothesis Two

The simple linear regression statistics were computed and presented on the Table 4.3:

Table 4.3: Simple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-Value	Remark	R	R^2	Adj R^2	F-ratio
Constant	0.045	3.258	0.001	Significant	0.134	0.018	0.009	0.176, p>0.05
CAG	0.005	0.42	0.675	Insignificant				

*Dependent Variable=PRT

Source: Researchers' Computation (2023)

From Table 4.3, CAG exerted positive and insignificant influence on PRT ($p>0.05$) of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It indicated that a percentage increase in CAG resulted to 0.5% increase in PRT. A constant value showed that PRT was 4.5% as CAG was held constant and significant ($p<0.05$). The constant value of 4.5% also showed that the quoted companies had been making some profits without CAG. The CAG was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers of the present study. The correlation coefficient (r) indicated that the relationship between CAG and PRT was 13.4%. R^2 (coefficient of determination) showed that 1.8% variation in the PRT was attributed to the influence of CAG in the model. The F-ratio (0.176, prob.>0.05) calculated indicated that the model was not significant. The null hypothesis, which stated that current asset growth does not significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that current asset growth significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected because both t-statistics and the p-value showed that CAG was not significant.

4.1.2.3 Hypothesis Three

The simple linear regression statistics were computed and presented on the Table 4.4:

Table 4.4: Simple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-Value	Remark	R	R ²	Adj R ²	F-ratio
Constant	0.032	3.2	0.0010	Significant	0.734	0.539	0.531	48.50, p<0.05
NAG	0.482	22.95	0.0000	Significant				

*Dependent Variable=PRT

Source: Researchers' Computation (2023)

From Table 4.4, NAG exerted positive and significant influence on PRT ($p < 0.05$) of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It indicated that a percentage increase in NAG resulted to 48.2% increase in PRT. A constant value showed that PRT was 3.2% as NAG was held constant and significant ($p < 0.05$). The constant value of 3.2% also indicated that the quoted companies had been making some profits without NAG. The NAG was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers of the present study. The correlation coefficient (r) indicated that the relationship between NAG and PRT was 73.4%. R² (coefficient of determination) showed that 53.9% variation in the PRT was attributed to the influence of NAG in the model. The F-ratio (48.50, prob.<0.05) calculated indicated that the model was significant. The null hypothesis, which stated that net asset growth does not significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that net asset growth significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted because both t-statistics and the p-value showed that NAG was significant.

4.1.2.4 Hypothesis Four

The simple linear regression statistics were computed and presented on the Table 4.5:

Table 4.5: Simple Linear Regression Output

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-Value	Remark	R	R ²	Adj R ²	F-ratio
Constant	0.088	4.889	0.000	Significant	0.791	0.626	0.62	55.23, p<0.05
TAG	0.547	12.721	0.000	Significant				

*Dependent Variable=PRT

Source: Researchers' Computation (2023)

From Table 4.5, TAG exerted positive and significant influence on PRT ($p < 0.05$) of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. It indicated that a percentage increase in TAG resulted to 54.7% increase in PRT. A constant value showed that PRT was 8.8% as TAG was held constant and significant ($p < 0.05$). The constant value of 8.8% also indicated that the quoted companies had been making some profits without TAG. The TAG was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers of the present study. The correlation coefficient (r) indicated that the

relationship between TAG and PRT was 79.1%. R^2 (coefficient of determination) showed that 62.6% variation in the PRT was attributed to the influence of TAG in the model. The F-ratio (55.23, prob.<0.05) calculated indicated that the model was significant. The null hypothesis, which stated that total asset growth does not significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which stated that total asset growth significantly influence profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted because both t-statistics and the p-value showed that TAG was significant.

4.2 Discussion of the Findings

From Table 4.2, non-current assets growth (NCAG) indicated positive and significant influence on profitability (PRT) of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The NCAG was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers. When non-current assets of a company grow, managers of the firm are always on the view that profitability should be improved as well because the components of non-current assets often show the level of expansion and investments of the company which is usually expected to have a direct influence on profitability. This is why non-current asset growth in this study had positive and significant influence on the profitability of the entities studied. Also, as managers of firm continued to acquire more components of non-current asset, the aim of such acquisitions should always be stated vividly so that the purpose of investing in those assets can meet the expectation of the managers in terms of adequate revenue generation. When the components of non-current asset are acquired beyond the intended purpose, the costs of investing in such assets might not be recovered from the benefits of those assets and thus, profitability might also be affected negatively.

This study was in line with Inyiama *et al.* (2017) who evaluated the level of association between assets growth rate and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria and from the analysis, it was discovered that non-current assets growth rate positively and powerfully related with the profit after tax.

From Table 4.3, Current Asset Growth (CAG) exerted positive and insignificant influence on Profitability (PRT) of the quoted manufacturing entities in Nigeria. This was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers in the study. Accumulation of more current assets by an entity usually affect profitability negatively. That is why it is often expected that current assets should be kept as low as possible in order that profitability is not affected negatively. Thus, larger growth in current assets could affect profitability of companies negatively. For CAG to influence profitability of firms positively, it therefore implies that the total current assets of these entities are maintained as low as possible. In the case of the present study, current assets of the quoted manufacturing entities used in this study were kept low during the period chosen for this research and this is why the average of CAG was 21.55% which is even less than fifty percent (50%).

This study was not in consistent with Irungu (2017) who investigated the effect of liquidity on financial performance of listed firms in the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE) and from the analysis, it was discovered that there was a positive and significant association between liquidity and profitability of financial and non-financial firms. The deviation in the findings could be attributed to the fact that the study of Irungu (2017) was done in another country with its economic imperatives and the proxies of liquidity were used as the predictors.

From Table 4.4, Net Asset Growth (NAG) had positive and significant influence on Profitability (PRT) of the listed non-financial entities in Nigeria. The results of the analysis with regard to NAG was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers. Net assets of any entities have to do with amount of assets that are financed by long-term capital, which are both long-term debt and equity. The composition of net assets is non-current assets plus current assets and less current liabilities. When current liabilities of an entity are higher, the expectation is that net asset must be lower in the accounting period. Also, for net asset growth to affect profitability positively and significantly, the proportion of current asset growth must not be higher than the proportion of non-current asset growth as higher current asset growth usually has inverse relationship with profitability of companies. In the present study, NAG was discovered to have positive and significant influence on PRT which indicated that during the period in which data were collected for the study, the proportion of non-current asset was higher than that of current assets maintained by the companies over the years. This study was in line with Inyiama *et al.* (2017) who studied the level of association between assets growth rate and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria and from the findings, it was observed that net asset growth rate of the companies positively and strongly related with the profit after tax.

From Table 4.5, Total Asset Growth (TAG) had positive and significant influence on Profitability (PRT) of the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. TAG was in compliance with *a priori* expectation stated by the researchers in the model. This implies that a naira increases in TAG could result to improvement in PRT of the companies studied. The composition of total assets maintained by these entities studied had greater proportion of non-current assets compared to current assets. This is why TAG in the study had direct and significant influence on PRT. Non-current assets are often thought to drive revenue directly when they are properly accumulated and managed by managers of entities according to researchers. This is why the composition of total assets are usually expected to have more of non-current assets than current assets as idle funds do not generate returns. This study was in consistent with Ugwu & Eze (2018) who conducted a study to empirically determine the effect of firms' growth indices on profitability of food and beverage firms in Nigeria and from the analysis, it was observed that total assets had significant effect on firm performance in Nigeria.

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

5.1 Conclusion

The purpose of the study was to ascertain the influence of asset growth on profitability of the quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. From the findings of this study, it was concluded that asset growth had positive and significant influence on profitability of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Non-Current Asset Growth (NCAG), Net Asset Growth (NAG) and Total Asset Growth (TAG) had positive and significant influence on profitability (PRT) and Current Asset Growth (CAG) had positive and insignificant influence on PRT of the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

5.2 Implications of the Study

From the outcomes of the analysis, the following implications were suggested such as first, non-current assets should be acquired and accumulated by the listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria as non-current asset growth had positive and significant influence on profitability of these companies. Second, management of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria should invest more in current asset of their companies in order to raise the growth in current assets as this will have a positive influence on profitability of the entities. Third, the management of the quoted manufacturing entities in Nigeria should formulate policies of accumulating assets that are capable of boosting the revenue of the companies and as well as raising the returns in terms of profitability. Finally, the composition of current assets of these companies should be made up of highly liquid assets that can be easily convertible to meet obligations that could impact on revenue generation of these companies.

5.3 Limitations and Direction for Further Studies

The study would have been extended to quoted financial service companies, but the mode of operations is not the same with other listed companies in Nigeria. The study was limited to parametric statistical tools with their limitations. However, asset growth and profitability of individuals sub-sectors, used in these studies, should be researched further and asset growth and profitability of manufacturing companies in Nigeria should be studied with the used of profitability ratios of Returns on Equity (ROE) and Return on Capital Employed (ROCE).

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